

Browser Security: There's No Winning A Cyberwar On Contested Ground

Waseem Arif, Menlo Security

Summary - Software vendors have recently claimed that installing a replacement browser will address the secure access and data security requirements of the modern enterprise and protect users as well. Fundamental limitations in such a product architecture undermine such claims. Replacement browsers on corporate endpoints exhibit flaws that can increase security risk. Relying on local software on an untrusted device for security controls exposes an enterprise to risks that cannot be easily mitigated. Resident malware, malicious insiders, and an expanded vulnerability surface result in a situation where the security risk is increased with such additional local software. Secure enterprise browsing requires browsers to enter the cloud era and use a separation strategy, employing distributed, cloud-based isolation. A cloud-based approach eliminates browser-based threats by processing and rendering content in the cloud, safeguarding data and securing web sessions. This paper explores the underlying limitations and security risks associated with replacement browsers running locally on an endpoint device.

LANDSCAPE AND PROBLEM SPACE

Today's dispersed workforce and the complex application landscape have evolved significantly since even 2019. Enterprises must address this change as threats are growing more sophisticated and adopting evasive tactics.¹ Enterprises are struggling with the risk and the costs of providing secure access to Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) platforms and to private applications. Managing Bring-Your-Own-Device (BYOD) deployments and securing access for 3rd parties/contractors pose additional risks and require further investment. Virtual Desktop Infrastructure (VDI) and traditional network security implementations, such as remote access VPNs, have proven to be a weak point and have been breached repeatedly. That weakness and the costs associated with this technology (which is rooted in 1990s and 2000s architectures and protocols) have spurred a need for modernization. Yet organizations continue to struggle with the complexities of providing seamless connectivity to the workforce while safeguarding sensitive data.²

Organizations rely on both SaaS applications for productivity and on licensed and custom internal applications for critical operations. Ensuring secure access

control and robust data protection across these environments is essential. Data governance vulnerabilities within SaaS platforms, along with shared credentials, and insider threats pose ongoing risks. Enterprises must bolster the defense of these assets, regardless of where they reside, without compromising data security. They must provide access to employees and partners that are dispersed and not at a central site. Personal devices, including laptops and mobile devices, often access enterprise applications. Expanding trust boundaries to encompass users and devices without risking data security is required and is also a crucial component of risk management. Approaches must balance accessibility and security as the traditional workplace boundaries expand to multiple locations and devices. These same needs often extend to third-party access as well. Third-party contractor access further complicates managing risk and effective security controls are essential to prevent breaches and protect sensitive information.³

THE SPECTRUM OF APPROACHES

In pursuit of solutions, especially during the COVID-driven "work-from-home" era, organizations have grappled with using legacy systems, such as VDI implementations or legacy remote-access VPNs. Deploying them in a secure and cost-effective manner proved difficult. The urgency to expand the footprint of VPNs resulted in enterprises sometimes ignoring the risks of connecting networks in order to connect users with the applications they need to work. Further, the pursuit of a solution to "We need access tomorrow!" led to the use of imperfect tools. VDI has consistently disappointed end-users from a digital experience perspective, and the public-facing systems required to make VDI work for remote access have been exploited again and again, and again. VDI and traditional VPNs are antiquated, costly and risky⁴. Other technologies emerged as options for a better fit. As browser-isolation evolved, secure cloud browsing has arrived with capabilities to address the need for secure access to public and private applications. Local browser isolation grew from an endpoint security and browser defense technology into the offer of replacement browsers known as "Enterprise Browsers." These replacement browsers and secure cloud browsing pose an alternative to desktop sharing and VDI and remote access VPNs. Replacement browsers have packed more functionality into client host machines. This can include a

¹ <https://cloud.google.com/security/resources/m-trends>

² <https://www.cisa.gov/news-events/cybersecurity-advisories/aa24-060b>

³ <https://csrc.nist.gov/pubs/sp/800/207/final>

⁴ <https://thehackernews.com/2024/05/ivanti-patches-critical-remote-code.html>

remote browsing client and a VPN client. Some replacement browsers even include integrated AI chat and person-to-person messaging. The evolution of browser defense and their application to expanded use cases invites a deeper exploration of the limitations of replacement browsers. Local replacement browsers attempting to secure access to applications and assets on untrusted devices are akin to adding a blast door to a straw hut, and run counter to trusted and proven “defense in depth” and layered-security architectures.⁵

SECURITY CLAIMS MUST BE SCRUTINIZED

Enterprise browser vendors claim to address a broad set of use cases, extending beyond defensive controls and encompassing secure access for multi-user PC environments, zero trust deployments and network-oriented “secure edge” applications. When made by developers of local replacement browser software, these claims are not sustainable in real-world deployments. Such claims are based on security assumptions and on assertions that are outdated and misaligned with the threat environment and with the needs of enterprise security organizations. The enthusiasm of marketing has inflated these claims to a point that they border on security “snake oil” or “security theater.”

The functionality required to address the browser security use cases must, at least, successfully perform the following operations:

- **Protect the local client/endpoint** - minimize the risk that a user is compromised when visiting a malicious site.
- **Protect the data** - prevent the unauthorized use of data by the user or a malicious actor on the endpoint or in the middle of a transaction.
- **Protect the server/application** - minimize the risk that a malicious client can exploit a vulnerability in a web application.

Local replacement browsers do not meet these requirements.

LIMITATION #1: LOCAL EXPLOITS

Replacement browsers (or “Enterprise Browsers” as they have been marketed) cannot protect the local client from Internet-borne threats. Current and emerging threats can evade both network and endpoint security controls, leaving the browser to play the role of beachhead or bastion. Google Chrome and the Chromium open-source browser project have been responsible for a renaissance in web browsing technology, and around 80% of modern browsers use Chromium open-source technologies. Any such widely adopted technology becomes a target, and the Chromium architecture is not immune to the energy of threat actors .

Chromium-based browsers are a rich target: users today spend 75% of their time in web browsers and web conferences. Most of them are based on Chromium. Usage spans checking email, accessing SaaS applications, private applications, or general web surfing. The threat landscape has shifted and increasingly targets browsers. Ninety-eight percent (98%) of cyber attacks originate from internet usage and eighty percent (80%) of those attacks target the browser.

Malicious websites can attempt to exploit a vulnerability in the Chrome browser. Each year, attackers discover numerous flaws that could allow attackers to steal sensitive data entered into seemingly trusted websites, such as usernames, passwords, or financial information. In a single year, Chrome experiences hundreds of potential vulnerabilities, a constant risk for users, with many allowing for potential data theft or device compromise. In 2023 alone, there were over 175 vulnerabilities discovered in Chrome and many have been actively exploited by threat actors.⁶

The primary architectural flaw stems from replacement browsers leveraging Chromium for their underlying architecture and from that local installation of a duplicate, replacement browser. Any Chromium based vulnerability will be inherited by any software built on Chromium. Replacement browsers incorporate Chromium into their own software, actually expanding the attack surface. Depending on the scope of modifications and additions to the original Chromium source, such applications may invalidate the security measures taken by Google and with the Chromium project. Any such application must replicate the same scope and depth of security testing and controls that Google and Chromium collaborators have developed.

So beyond the expanded attack surface, the risk of less rigor in the overall security testing of the combined solution actually generates risk. This risk is especially concerning because the integration of Chromium happens directly on the endpoint device itself, exposing the entire device to exploits. In contrast, cloud technologies separate the local endpoint from threats, and can simplify managing updates to the browser that may be exposed to threats—because it operates within a cloud that applies additional security and because updates can be completed in an automated fashion even if the user device is offline or has poor internet connectivity.

⁵ <https://www.gartner.com/document/4274299>

⁶https://www.cvedetails.com/vulnerability-list/vendor_id-1224/product_id-15031/

Sample Exploited Chrome Vulnerabilities

[CVE-2023-2033 – Type Confusion in V8](#)

[CVE-2023-2136 – Integer overflow in the Skia graphics library](#)

[CVE-2023-3079 – Type Confusion in V8](#)

[CVE-2023-4863 – Heap buffer overflow in WebP](#)

[CVE-2023-5217 – Heap buffer overflow in vp8 encoding in libvpx](#)

[CVE-2023-6345 – Integer overflow in Skia graphics library](#)

[CVE-2023-4762 – Type Confusion in V8](#)

DEBILITATING MITIGATION

Proponents of replacement browsers assert that disabling browser functionality reduces the risk that a browser vulnerability will lead to a breach. Disabling little used features leaves a significant attack surface for attackers to exploit. Disabling protocols that enable voice and video within browser applications (WebRTC) or removing support for advanced graphics (WebGL) leaves several available exploits and impedes advanced uses of modern web browsers. Disabling functionality that is broadly available in standard browsers is not a sustainable approach as Enterprise applications inevitably come to rely on these features. Several of the highlighted exploits from 2023 remain possible even with such features disabled.

LIMITATIONS OF EMBEDDED SECURITY FEATURES

Proponents of replacement browsers assert that operating system and processor optimizations, such as Control Flow Guard (CFG), Control-flow Enforcement Technology (CET), and Arbitrary Code Guard (ACG) provide protection against exploits. While such controls make memory corruption attacks more difficult, they do not provide complete protection. These controls are necessary, but insufficient. They do not prevent bugs that allow for arbitrary code execution, and they have been widely circumvented as well. Moreover, CFG, CET, and ACG are already available in leading browsers supplied by Google or Microsoft. Employing these features makes exploitation more difficult, but attackers have overcome them. Time and again, as evidenced by the continued successful exploitation of browser zero-day exploits, these defenses have been defeated. While they have increased the cost of exploitation for attackers, they have not made exploiting most

vulnerabilities impossible, and the leading browsers are best equipped to combat such attacks.⁷

ONGOING UPDATES AND FEATURE MAINTENANCE

Replacement browsers are built on Chromium, effectively doubling the exposure to Chromium vulnerabilities on the local endpoint when they are installed—unless the resident Chromium-based browser is removed. The original resident browser must be removed or managed to avoid leaving an exposure in place, which introduces the additional burden of ensuring that both browsers are “managed.” One browser must be patched and managed and every other browser, the browsers that users prefer, must be removed permanently. Management requires more than just up to date software. Forcing the installation of the latest version when it becomes available is important, but just as critical is deploying and enforcing a secure configuration policy.

The providers of leading browsers update them frequently, on a monthly or even weekly basis. When they update these browsers to fix vulnerabilities, they may also provide new functionality. There is no long term stable release of Chromium that only includes bug and security fixes. Unless this new functionality is intentionally disabled, new attack surface is introduced. In some cases, as when a whole new API is added, it may be relatively simple to disable. In other cases, the new features are changes to existing APIs that are not so easy to disable. Disabling functionality might also break websites or web applications that attempt to use the functionality.

Duplicating the browser creates another application that must be managed. This duplication results in thousands of settings that must be under policy and hundreds of vulnerabilities annually that present a concern. And it multiplies the work by two unless the extant browser is completely removed. Managing the installed local browser is an opportunity to improve security and introduce a “defense in depth” or “layered security” model to browsers—but duplicating that attack surface increases risk.

SUSTAINABLE PROTECTION FROM THREATS

To effectively defend against threats, security practitioners need to remove the attack surface where possible and manage the points of attack where exposure remains. Completely taking the browser “off the table” as a beachhead for threat actors is an option that has emerged as remote browser isolation evolved and matured into fully developed secure cloud browsing. Rather than merely picking and choosing functionality to turn off in the local

⁷<https://i.blackhat.com/Asia-22/Friday-Materials/AS-22-Zhang-Bypass-CFG-In-Chrome.pdf>

browser, enterprises can run a browser in a secure cloud so that users' local endpoints are never exposed to attacks. Secure cloud browsing creates a digital twin of the tabs and web content that users need and enables the user to work with a web application without being exposed to internet-borne threats (Cloud browsing also protects private web applications, because they can be made available to remote users without being exposed to the Internet.).

As new functionality is added to the browser (from within the Chromium open-source project), a secure cloud browser can withhold that functionality until it has been evaluated by a security team. For example, there is no need to identify WebGL as a source of security issues. Instead, WebGL is simply not used on the client-side unless explicitly required and thoroughly analyzed. If such a feature is enabled within the local resident browser, content that would exploit a vulnerability cannot reach the local browser because websites are not directly accessed. Cloud browsing separates local browsers and web apps from threats that would attempt to abuse an API or exploit a vulnerability maliciously. For example, with cloud browsing, the Geolocation API, while useful, is never exposed to untrusted JavaScript; Instead, all interactions occur through secure, managed calls within a layered security model that combines management of the local browser with secure cloud browsing.

A secure cloud browsing system that works with the local browser does not force the customer to choose between not supporting a feature and creating risk. Instead, the feature can be safely leveraged in the cloud: All the WebGL happens in the cloud. And just-in-time (JIT) compilation for JavaScript, another feature that has been the subject of attacks, happens in the cloud. (Disabling JIT compilation can significantly slow down JS heavy pages. Using JIT in a secure cloud browser is safe and performs well.). The replacement browser approach hobbles the end user in the name of security, providing a poor experience. History has shown that users attempt to circumvent controls that degrade their experience.

A layered security model manages the local browser and uses a secure, up-to-date cloud browser. A cloud browser acts as a hardened digital twin for the local browser and reduces the risk of accessing web content. By separating the local browser and its twin, updates can be completed even if a user device is powered off or connecting through a low bandwidth link (where pushing large updates is not practical). Another benefit of the cloud browser is that enterprise-application tabs can be separated from personal browser tabs. Even cookie storage can be segregated. And these controls can be transparent to the end user.

LIMITATION #2: PROTECTING SENSITIVE DATA

Endpoint-based security measures, like Data Loss Prevention (DLP) and Data Redaction, are growing increasingly important. As network-based DLP grows more difficult due to pervasive TLS encryption and the rise of remote work with SaaS apps, endpoint approaches to DLP have emerged because DLP has grown increasingly impractical via network controls alone. Endpoint-based DLP that operates outside of an organization's domain of control can be circumvented. Replacement browsers attempt to stop digital leakage at the client endpoint. The weakness in this approach is the architecture: such approaches rely on potentially compromised devices to enforce controls.

Scans, filters, and masking are ultimately powerless to protect sensitive data that has reached the endpoint. Once it resides, even temporarily, within the device's memory, malicious software can steal the information. This exposure stems from sensitive data needing to pass through the local system memory for rendering. Local security mechanisms are applied only after the data has reached the endpoint. A recent zero-day Windows exploit (CVE-2024-21338) underscores the futility of relying on end-point controls within replacement browsers: Even a 'secure' local browser is powerless on an untrusted endpoint (BYOD). When attackers gain kernel-level control, user-space redaction and encryption of sensitive data becomes a pointless charade.

DATA ACCESS SECURITY

Browsers and applications work together to restrict access to sensitive data through features like hardened configurations, extension controls, and conditional access policies. However, these access-centric approaches offer a false sense of security when access tokens are present on the untrusted device. Those session tokens are ripe for theft. Despite claims of securing applications, browsers ultimately fail to adequately safeguard sensitive data due to their underlying architecture. After an attacker has compromised an endpoint, access restrictions fall apart. Techniques such as token theft, browser impersonation, and exploiting application authorization flaws render browser-level protections moot, allowing unauthorized data access.⁸

ENDPOINT STORAGE IS NO ANSWER

Replacement browsers can store local data within an encrypted container on the device. As an on-endpoint application, the container can be hidden from a system's regular file system. Such an approach enables a user to work

⁸<https://resources.menlosecurity.com/reports/global-cyber-gangs-supported-and-sheltered-by-state-sponsors-and-getting-smarter-every-day>

with files and it can also apply controls or block the user from copying the file outside of the virtual file system. While these controls can stop many potential misuses by insiders, a malicious insider or an attacker with elevated privileges can bypass such controls and access sensitive data directly: the data is present in memory unencrypted (prior to being encrypted on disk) and the encrypting keys are present in device memory. For a skilled and motivated threat actor, such controls are no defense.

CLOUD-DRIVEN BROWSER SECURITY

There exist mitigations for DLP and the risks of exposing sensitive data to a potentially contested endpoint. When a local browser works in cooperation with cloud-delivered security measures, DLP enforcement can be applied in the cloud, before sensitive data ever reaches the endpoint. Even with endpoint protection and security posture scans, endpoints need not be trusted more than necessary. Cloud browsing can ensure that sensitive information remains securely stored in the cloud, in a secure area, protected from local threats and vulnerabilities and protected from endpoint risks. Files can remain in the cloud and be transferred between SaaS applications without touching the endpoint. This cloud-driven approach prevents local malware, infected storage, and other endpoint-targeting strategies that are designed to exfiltrate or compromise sensitive files from gaining any foothold at all. This data protection extends beyond intellectual property and personally identifying information, and includes the authentication tokens that are the keys to a session. Redacted data is actually redacted, not just masked after it has already been delivered to the endpoint, and session tokens are never exposed to the endpoint browser.

LIMITATION #3: PROTECTING SERVERS AND APPLICATIONS

Replacement browsers claim protection at the client level, but the approach leaves unmitigated server-side exploits open to attack. Historically local client browsers interact directly with server web applications. This design assumption has left open a gap where attackers can use compromised endpoints as a launchpad. If an endpoint is compromised, then it can attack servers that are reachable. Some replacement browsers do employ an anti-tampering, “panic and shutdown,” tactic to address this scenario—but such tactics invoke defenses too late to be reliable.

When an attack compromises the underlying OS, even anti-tampering protection within the browser offers no practical mitigation. Further, replacement browsers offer no means to prevent server-side exploits. In cases like Log4Shell (where modified 'User-Agent' headers triggered the vulnerability) or Citrix Bleed (where the 'Host' header was exploited), an attacker can simply extract session tokens from a compromised endpoint and pivot to using their own modified browser to target the vulnerable applications.

“Panic-and-shutdown” mode relies on software defenses within the local machine’s operating system OS in addition to the replacement browser. Attackers with elevated privileges, such as those gained through exploits or rootkits can bypass these defenses. The replacement browsers have no mitigation for kernel-level attacks that circumvent process or memory isolation or that inject malicious code directly into the trusted browser process.

LIMITED CLOUD PROTECTION AND UNTRUSTED DEVICES

Replacement browsers attempt some data protection locally, but struggle to maintain data sovereignty in all cloud interactions. If an attacker breaches the user device, organizational data and systems beyond the local endpoint become vulnerable despite any protections the browser itself provides. A 2023 report by Verizon found that 82% of data breaches involved compromised credentials, which often happen through endpoint devices.

The fundamental issue rests in the untrusted device itself. To be reliable, software requires a "full chain of trust", rooted in hardware. Even hardware-level defenses such as memory encryption can be undermined by micro-architectural attacks on modern CPUs (Spectre, Meltdown). This means an endpoint device must be considered inherently risk-prone.

CLOUD BROWSING HALTS INTERNET-BORNE THREATS

Generation-one browser isolation technology heralded the need for augmented browser security. Replacement browsers correlate strongly to attempts at local browser isolation from the Mid-2010s. Application “shielding” and local sandboxes have largely been subsumed by leading browsers and operating-system capabilities. Such defenses have proven necessary but insufficient. Duplicating these defenses in a replacement browser does not solve the problem of browser security; it multiplies the attack surface.

Remote browser isolation, in contrast, has been widely deployed and has been included within leading security and network security products and services. It has demonstrably reduced phishing and malware attacks, and it has forced attackers to use other means, such as person-to-person social engineering tactics. Even so, time has passed and threats have changed in other ways. RBI needed to evolve to remain a cost-effective and efficacious system that could address modern threats and support work in the mid-2020s and beyond. Secure cloud browsing is the next generation of RBI. Secure cloud browsing offers the following benefits that replacement browsers cannot offer:

- **Eliminates Direct Access:** User traffic never reaches the application directly, Cloud browsing prevents endpoint compromise from being

leveraged as an attack vector.

- **Server-Side Protection:** Cloud browsing mitigates server-side vulnerabilities and zero-day exploits that local browsers cannot address.
- **Data Security:** Read-only access and strict input controls empower safe access to sensitive applications and the associated data, even on untrusted devices.
- **Cloud Isolation and Least-Privilege Access:** The user does not control the remote OS where the browser executes. The attack surface is limited to mouse and keyboard inputs. OS-level processes and the application are simply unavailable to users (and attackers). This control limits threat-actor capabilities even on a compromised endpoint.

Security practitioners and network security engineers are using secure cloud browsing to protect users from attacks aimed at local browsers. Cloud-delivered security can secure access to sensitive data on private applications and apply policy to public SaaS applications as well. Local replacement browsers cannot reliably achieve this goal because the local endpoint remains a rich attack surface. Replacement browsers repeat the mistake of local browser isolation sandboxes, offering insufficient protection due to their reliance on the potentially compromised endpoint and bloating the local system with additional capabilities that invite attack. This architecture exposes the local system to malicious actions and application and system-level vulnerabilities.

SECURE ENTERPRISE BROWSING

Cloud browsing works with a local browser to secure enterprise browsing. Cloud-delivered security provides a layered solution, addressing the core shortcomings of endpoint-centric approaches. Importantly, secure cloud browsing appeals to users, enabling them to retain the local browser they prefer, which discourages attempts at circumvention. Cloud browsing removes the risk of even the most evasive attacks, dramatically reducing the risks arising from malicious activity, browser vulnerabilities, and compromised devices.

Cloud browsing has emerged to finally solve the problem of browser targeted attacks with a provably reliable approach, an architecture that mitigates risk by decoupling interactions and untrusted web content and code execution from endpoints while allowing safe and efficient content usage. Rather than throwing out leading browsers—the most

pervasive application in history⁹—enterprises must secure them through thoughtful application of management, protective controls, and controls that enable secure access to applications and associated data without creating new risks or driving up costs so high that security controls cannot be pervasively deployed.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Waseem Arif, Senior Technical Marketing Engineer
Menlo Security

<https://www.menlosecurity.com>.

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⁹ An esteemed reviewer has noted that Microsoft Solitaire may well be the most popular enterprise application. Touché